

Master's Thesis

**Choosing Through Fear: Trauma-Related Symptoms and Biased Decision-Making in
Aversive Contexts**

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Abstract

This study investigated how trauma-related symptoms influence decision-making under aversive conditions. Eighty-seven participants completed a modified two-armed bandit task that included unpredictable exposure to aversive screams, with emotional intensity manipulated across trials. Trauma symptoms were assessed using the International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ), capturing dimensions of PTSD and Complex PTSD (CPTSD). Bias persistence was assessed via choice behavior and belief updating, while anticipatory skin conductance responses (SCRs) indexed physiological arousal. Higher PTSD symptom severity was associated with greater bias persistence and reduced belief updating, reflecting impaired cognitive flexibility. In contrast, higher levels of Disturbances in Self-Organization (DSO), a CPTSD symptom cluster, were linked to greater adaptability. Emotional intensity did not moderate these effects, and trauma symptoms did not predict SCR responses. These findings suggest that PTSD symptoms contribute to rigid decision-making, while CPTSD may involve distinct cognitive response patterns.

Keywords: bias persistence, Complex PTSD, PTSD, skin conductance response, two-armed bandit task, decision-making under uncertainty

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Choosing Through Fear: Trauma-Related Symptoms and Biased Decision-Making in Aversive Contexts

Introduction

Decision-Making Under Uncertainty

Decision-making under uncertainty is a foundational cognitive process that affects human behavior across numerous contexts. From daily decisions to high-stakes decisions, people have to frequently negotiate incomplete knowledge, uncertain results, and emotionally charged consequences. Within this setting, they are required to continuously balance the need to explore new information against the desire to exploit previously learned beneficial outcomes (Cohen et al., 2007). This dynamic, known as the exploration versus exploitation trade-off, is critical for adaptive behavior and becomes particularly important under conditions of instability or emotional salience, as these contexts often require rapid reassessment of goals and strategies (Cohen, McClure, & Yu, 2007).

When emotional arousal is high, cognitive control mechanisms can become compromised. Individuals may favor immediate, emotionally reassuring responses over slower, more reflective decisions (Ochsner & Gross, 2005). This tendency contributes to bias persistence, a cognitive phenomenon where individuals maintain an initial belief or behavioral preference even after receiving contradictory evidence (Harris et al., 2020). Bias persistence can be seen as a breakdown in adaptive learning. In emotionally arousing or uncertain situations, people tend to rely more on exploitation strategies. They prefer familiar and safe options instead of exploring new ones (Cohen et al., 2007). This limits exposure to disconfirming information and makes it more likely that existing beliefs will persist. This rigidity can be particularly pronounced in aversive environments where cognitive and emotional demands are high, leading individuals to favor exploitation over exploration. As a result, they miss opportunities to encounter disconfirming evidence, which can reinforce and prolong early biases (Harris et al., 2020). Such conditions tend to exacerbate attentional narrowing, threat prioritization, and impulsive responding, impairing rational decision-making (Gagne et al., 2020). Emotional arousal in such situations is not only shaped by the immediate environment but also by individuals' past experiences. For example, people with Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) symptoms often exhibit heightened emotional reactivity and altered learning in response to threat cues. These changes may influence how they approach the exploration-exploitation trade-off, potentially favoring rigid, habitual

responses over adaptive flexibility (Paulus & Yu, 2012). When decision-makers rely too heavily on exploitation, they limit their sampling of alternative options. This biased information gathering can entrench initial preferences and impair learning, and this effect may be further intensified in individuals with trauma-related symptoms. This highlights the importance of investigating how decision-making in aversive contexts is shaped by PTSD-related traits, which is the central focus of the present study.

Trauma and Maladaptive Decision Patterns

Given that emotionally arousing and aversive contexts can impair decision-making and reduce cognitive flexibility, it is important to consider individual differences that may intensify these effects. One such factor is post-traumatic stress symptomatology, which has been shown to significantly influence how individuals make decisions under emotional stress (Aupperle et al., 2012; Paulus & Yu, 2012). Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) is characterized by a constellation of symptoms including intrusive recollections, avoidance behavior, emotional hyperarousal, and alterations in memory and attention (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). These symptoms not only reflect emotional distress but also disrupt core cognitive processes necessary for adaptive decision-making, potentially affecting how individuals balance exploration and exploitation in uncertain or threatening environments. This over-reliance on exploitation can limit exposure to disconfirming evidence, reinforcing early assumptions and leading to a persistence of initial preferences or judgments (Aupperle et al., 2012; Harris et al., 2020).

More recently, the International Classification of Diseases (ICD-11) has introduced the diagnosis of Complex PTSD (CPTSD), which includes the core symptoms of PTSD along with Disturbances in Self-Organization (DSO). These disturbances consist of affective dysregulation, negative self-concept, and interpersonal dysfunction (Maercker et al., 2013). These additional features reflect a broader and more chronic disruption in psychological functioning. Individuals with CPTSD may demonstrate chronic difficulties in regulating emotions, shifting cognitive strategies, or engaging flexibly with uncertainty (Hyland et al., 2017). These traits are especially relevant in decision-making contexts that require individuals to tolerate uncertainty, re-evaluate prior judgments, and modulate emotional responses to unexpected outcomes.

Neurocognitive Mechanisms Linking Trauma and Bias

The relationship between trauma and cognitive inflexibility is underpinned by well-documented neurobiological mechanisms. Functional imaging studies have shown that individuals with PTSD or CPTSD exhibit increased amygdala activation in response to emotional stimuli, alongside reduced prefrontal cortex regulation, particularly in regions associated with top-down control and working memory (Etkin & Wager, 2007; Aupperle et al., 2012). This neural imbalance, characterized by heightened amygdala activation and reduced prefrontal cortex (PFC) engagement, compromises the brain's ability to suppress automatic threat responses and flexibly integrate new information. When PFC activity is diminished, individuals are less able to inhibit automatic responses and are more likely to interpret ambiguous or neutral stimuli as threatening. Reduced PFC functioning also impairs working memory and cognitive flexibility, which are essential for updating existing cognitive schemas in light of new, potentially contradictory, information (Etkin et al., 2011; Ochsner & Gross, 2005).

Such dysregulation translates into behavioral rigidity. Research shows that trauma-exposed individuals have impaired reward learning and diminished responsiveness to changing outcome contingencies, indicating decreased adaptability (Simmons et al., 2008). For individuals with CPTSD, these impairments are often compounded by pervasive negative self-appraisals and chronic hypervigilance, which can intensify threat sensitivity and limit adaptive learning (Karatzias et al., 2019). These tendencies may create a cognitive environment in which individuals default to previously reinforced, emotionally safer choices, even when potentially better alternatives are available. This reflects a core mechanism underlying bias persistence.

Although the cognitive effects of trauma have been widely studied, few empirical investigations have directly examined bias persistence as a function of trauma symptomatology. Most existing literature has focused on executive dysfunction in trauma-exposed individuals or on general fear-processing mechanisms. However, decision-making tasks that require belief updating across repeated trials, particularly under emotionally arousing conditions, provide a more ecologically valid method for assessing real-world decision behavior in trauma-affected populations (Hopper et al., 2008).

Experimental Task: Aversive Adaptation of the Two-Armed Bandit

To investigate these processes, the present study employs a modified version of the two-armed bandit task developed by Harris et al. (2020). The task consisted of two phases: a Bias Induction Phase designed to establish an initial preference, followed by a Free Sampling Phase in which participants could revise their beliefs based on new feedback. In the original version, participants selected between two options associated with probabilistic rewards. One option initially appeared to be more rewarding, leading to the formation of a preference. Despite there being no difference in reward probabilities between the two choice alternatives, participants often continued to choose their preferred option in the condition where rewards were frequent, illustrating bias persistence driven by reinforcement frequency in reward-rich environments.

This study adapts the task to an aversive context by replacing rewarding outcomes with emotionally negative stimuli. One of the probabilistic outcome is paired with a loud, unpleasant human scream, so that the omission of this aversive stimulus serves as a form of reinforcement. To manipulate emotional intensity, participants are randomly assigned to one of two experimental conditions. In the Highly Aversive (HA) condition, the scream is presented in 75 percent of relevant trials. In the Less Aversive (LA) condition, the scream occurs in only 25 percent of relevant trials. This manipulation allows for the examination of whether emotional arousal intensifies bias persistence, particularly among individuals with elevated trauma symptoms.

While this task is adapted from Harris et al. (2020), the current study differs in both its theoretical framework and its central hypotheses. Harris and colleagues examined how reinforcement frequency in reward-rich environments consolidates early preferences through biased learning. Their findings demonstrated that when rewards are frequent, individuals are more likely to continue choosing an initially preferred option, even when the alternatives become equally or more rewarding. This form of bias persistence was interpreted as a function of positive reinforcement learning.

In contrast, the present study places its focus on how trauma-related symptomatology and emotional arousal influence belief updating and decision-making in a negatively valenced context. The task reverses the reinforcement structure by replacing rewards with aversive outcomes. Here, participants learn to avoid an emotionally negative stimulus (a

scream), meaning that reinforcement is linked to the absence of an outcome rather than its presence. As such, the condition with more frequent feedback (more screams) may lead to avoidance rather than preference. This reversal suggests that the relationship between reinforcement frequency and bias persistence could function quite differently than in the original reward-based version. The study therefore aims to investigate whether bias persistence in this aversive setting is better explained by emotional reactivity and trauma-related cognitive rigidity than by traditional reinforcement learning mechanisms.

The task involves a series of sequential decisions under uncertain feedback conditions, meaning that participants cannot predict with certainty which outcome will follow each choice. This design enables a detailed analysis of how trauma-related symptoms interact with emotionally aversive environments to influence learning, belief updating, and behavioral flexibility. To assess participants' emotional arousal, skin conductance responses are measured throughout the task.

Research Question and Hypotheses

This study investigates how trauma-related symptomatology (specifically PTSD and CPTSD symptoms) affects the persistence of cognitive bias during emotionally aversive decision-making. The central research question guiding this investigation is: In what ways do symptoms of PTSD and Complex PTSD influence bias persistence in an uncertain, emotionally aversive decision-making environment?

Based on existing theoretical and empirical literature, it is anticipated that individuals who report higher levels of PTSD symptoms will demonstrate stronger bias persistence. In the context of the current task, this is expected to manifest as limited updating of their contingency estimates following the Free Sampling Phase and a continued preference for the initially favored option, despite experiencing evidence that the alternative may yield more balanced or favorable outcomes (Simmons, Matthews, & Paulus, 2008; Aupperle et al., 2012). Furthermore, it is hypothesized that CPTSD symptoms (particularly those related to disturbances in self-organization, such as emotional dysregulation and negative self-concept) will be even more predictive of bias persistence than PTSD symptoms alone (Hyland et al., 2017; Cloitre et al., 2018). This stronger association is theorized to result from the broader impairments in cognitive flexibility and emotional regulation that characterize CPTSD (Karatzias et al., 2019).

The study also expects that the emotional intensity of the task environment will play a moderating role in these relationships. Specifically, it is predicted that the effects of trauma symptoms on bias persistence will be more pronounced in the Highly Aversive (HA) condition compared to the Less Aversive (LA) condition. The presence of frequent, emotionally salient stimuli (e.g., loud screams) is believed to increase physiological arousal and emotional load, which in turn may amplify trauma-related decision-making impairments (Phelps et al., 2014; Etkin et al., 2011).

Through this framework, the current study aims to offer a nuanced understanding of how different dimensions of trauma affect belief updating and behavioral flexibility in threatening contexts (Gagne et al., 2020).

Conceptual Framework and Theoretical Relevance

These hypotheses are grounded in a cognitive-affective framework, which proposes that decision-making results from the interaction between top-down control processes and bottom-up emotional inputs (Etkin et al., 2011; Paulus & Yu, 2012). From this perspective, trauma-related symptoms disrupt the balance between these systems, leading to maladaptive behaviors such as avoidance, cognitive rigidity, and biased learning. This disruption is hypothesized to be particularly potent in highly aversive environments, where emotional arousal competes with the need for reflective, data-driven decision-making (Phelps et al., 2014).

The study also draws from dual-process models of decision-making (Evans, 2008), which distinguish between intuitive, emotion-driven processes (System 1) and analytical, rule-based reasoning (System 2). Trauma exposure is believed to increase reliance on System 1, especially under stress, making individuals more susceptible to heuristic errors like bias persistence. Furthermore, theories of differential susceptibility suggest that trauma may heighten sensitivity to environmental conditions, amplifying maladaptive outcomes in threatening situations (Belsky & Pluess, 2009).

Practical Significance and Broader Implications

Understanding how trauma symptoms shape decision-making under stress has important implications for clinical psychology, behavioral science, and public health policy. Trauma-informed therapeutic interventions increasingly emphasize the need to restore cognitive

flexibility and emotional regulation in individuals with PTSD and CPTSD (Cloitre et al., 2012). Findings from this study may inform the development of cognitive retraining tools, exposure-based therapies, and decision-support systems that accommodate the emotional and cognitive profiles of trauma-exposed individuals.

Moreover, this research may help organizations design decision environments such as military training programs, therapeutic protocols, or educational frameworks that buffer against trauma-related cognitive biases. By highlighting the interaction between symptomatology, emotional context, and cognitive function, this study aims to contribute both theoretically and practically to the evolving field of trauma-informed decision science.

Methods

Participants

The study initially recruited 103 participants through a combination of sources: the FSBS Research Participation System (SONA), and direct outreach via the researchers' academic and social networks. Participants received either course credit or monetary compensation, depending on the recruitment channel. After applying exclusion criteria, the final sample comprised $N = 87$ participants. Specifically, 9 participants were excluded for failing to develop an initial bias during the task, 2 participants were removed for prematurely quitting the experiment (one during the Bias Induction Phase and one after only two trials in the Free Sampling Phase), and 5 participants indicated they had previously participated in a highly similar experiment.

All participants were fluent in English, reported no neurological or cardiological conditions, and had no hearing impairments. Informed consent was obtained from all participants in accordance with ethical guidelines approved by the university's ethics board (FETC approval number: 25-0088). Participants were randomly assigned to one of two aversive conditions (Highly Aversive vs. Less Aversive), and all procedures were standardized across conditions. The final sample size exceeded the threshold suggested by an a priori power analysis for a linear regression model with three predictors, which indicated that a minimum of 64 participants would be required to detect a moderate effect size ($f^2 = 0.15$) with 80% power at an alpha level of .05.

Procedure

Upon arrival at the laboratory, participants were greeted by the researcher, who provided a standardized written overview of the study (see Information Letter in Appendix A). All participants provided informed consent prior to beginning the experiment (see Appendix B).

Prior to electrode placement, participants were asked to wash their hands with water to ensure optimal skin electrode contact and reduce variability in skin conductance due to differences in hydration or surface impurities. Electrodes were attached to the distal phalanges of the index and middle fingers of the left hand. To determine eligibility for physiological data collection, participants first completed a standardized deep-breath test to assess the responsiveness of their electrodermal activity. This procedure is commonly used to verify normal sympathetic nervous system functioning prior to skin conductance recording and helps exclude participants who show little to no physiological variability (Boucsein et al., 2012). Only participants who demonstrated sufficient fluctuation in skin conductance during the test were permitted to continue with the full experiment.

Following this initial screening, participants were randomly assigned to one of two experimental conditions: the Highly Aversive (HA) condition, in which aversive outcomes occurred with a probability of 75%, or the Less Aversive (LA) condition, with a 25% aversive probability. Random assignment was implemented using computer-generated sequences to minimize experimenter bias and ensure group comparability (Field & Hole, 2003).

The experiment was administered via a computer interface in a lab room. The central experimental task was based on the aforementioned two-phase decision-making paradigm adapted from the probabilistic two-armed bandit task introduced by Harris et al. (2020). Before the start of the main task, participants were presented with a red button in the center of the screen. Clicking this button triggered the aversive noise (a loud human scream) at the same volume and intensity that would be used during the experiment. After hearing the sound, participants were explicitly asked whether they still wished to proceed. Only those who confirmed their willingness to continue were allowed to begin the task. In the Bias Induction Phase, participants completed a series of manipulated trials. They were told that the computer would randomly make the first few selections for them, to familiarize them with the task. However, unbeknownst to participants, evidence was deliberately presented unevenly: one bag was shown 12 times, with the frequent outcome occurring on 10 of those trials,

whereas the other bag was shown only 4 times, with the frequent outcome occurring in 3 trials. Despite the resulting contingency between choices and outcomes being negligible, this skewed presentation was expected to enhance the association between the frequent option and the frequent outcome, based on the pseudocontingency literature (Fiedler, 2000; Bott & Meiser, 2020). Participants were not informed of the exact probability distributions and were encouraged to rely on trial-and-error learning. At the end of this phase, participants were asked to provide explicit contingency estimates, which were subjective judgments of the probability of drawing a specific ball color from Bag A and Bag B, respectively. These self-reported estimates provided a baseline measure of initial bias formation.

Following this, half of the participants were shown a message stating that they had correctly identified the bag with the most blue or yellow balls. This was part of a separate manipulation for another research question, unrelated to the current hypotheses. It is not expected to have influenced participants' behavior in a way relevant to this study.

All participants were then informed that, going forward, one of the colors would now be paired with the aversive noise they had experienced earlier in the task. Specifically, they were told that one color would elicit the loud scream in certain trials, while the other would be paired with a softer white noise. The assignment of colors to sound types depended on their previously assigned condition (HA or LA), as described earlier.

Next, in the Free Sampling Phase, participants continued to make decisions between the same two options for 84 consecutive trials. This phase was designed to allow participants to revise their initial beliefs based on experience. Importantly, during this phase, one of the ball colors (blue or yellow) was now paired with an emotionally salient aversive stimulus (a brief human scream between 95 and 100 dB, delivered through headphones). The probability of experiencing the scream was manipulated based on the participant's assigned condition. Those in the HA condition encountered the aversive stimulus in 75% of the relevant trials, as it was paired with the frequent-colored ball. In contrast, those in the LA condition experienced it in only 25% of trials, since it was paired with the infrequent-colored ball. This manipulation ensured different levels of emotional arousal, allowing us to examine whether higher emotional intensity would increase bias persistence during decision-making (Phelps et al., 2014). These conditions systematically varied the emotional intensity of the task environment, with the HA condition simulating a high-stress context and the LA condition representing a comparatively milder emotional load. At the end of the Free Sampling Phase,

participants were again asked to provide contingency estimates to assess the extent to which they had updated their beliefs in response to outcome feedback.

Following the completion of the task, participants were asked to complete a battery of self-report questionnaires, including the International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ; see Appendix C), which measures both core PTSD and DSO symptoms in line with ICD-11 criteria (Cloitre et al., 2018). Participants also completed a brief demographic form capturing age, gender, language proficiency, and relevant medical history. Upon completion, electrodes were removed and participants were fully debriefed and compensated either through course credits or monetary payment, depending on the recruitment method.

The entire session lasted approximately 45 to 60 minutes. All procedures were carefully standardized to ensure consistency across participants and minimize extraneous variation that could confound the relationship between trauma symptoms and decision-making performance.

Measures

A multi-method measurement framework was used in this study to evaluate physiological arousal, behavioral indicators of bias persistence, and trauma symptomatology. In order to conduct an extensive study of how trauma-related symptoms impact judgment in emotionally aversive environments, these elements were operationalized through standardized self-report questionnaires, task-based behavioral metrics, and psychophysiological recordings.

Trauma Symptomatology

Participants' trauma-related symptoms were assessed using the *International Trauma Questionnaire* (ITQ; Cloitre et al., 2018), a self-report instrument developed to evaluate PTSD and CPTSD in accordance with the ICD-11 diagnostic criteria. The ITQ consists of two six-item symptom clusters. The first measures core PTSD symptoms, including re-experiencing, avoidance, and a heightened sense of threat. The second assesses Disturbances in Self-Organization (DSO), encompassing affective dysregulation, negative self-concept, and difficulties in interpersonal relationships.

Each symptom item is rated on a five-point Likert scale, ranging from 0 ("Not at all") to 4 ("Extremely"), with additional questions assessing functional impairment across life domains. In this study, total scores for the PTSD and DSO subscales were treated as

continuous variables to allow for a dimensional analysis of trauma symptoms. This approach is consistent with recent models of psychopathology that emphasize the spectrum nature of trauma-related distress (Hyland et al., 2017).

Behavioral Indicators of Bias Persistence

Bias persistence was assessed through two main behavioral measures derived from participants' performance on the modified two-armed bandit task: explicit contingency estimates and choice behavior.

Contingency estimates were collected at three points during the experiment. The first estimate was obtained immediately after the Bias Induction Phase, where participants were asked to estimate the probability of drawing each colored ball from each bag. This provided a baseline measure of initial bias formation. Following the Free Sampling Phase, participants completed two additional estimates. First, they were again asked to estimate the likelihood of drawing each color from each bag, allowing for an assessment of how much their beliefs had shifted based on the sampling experience. Immediately after this, they were asked to estimate the likelihood of experiencing an aversive noise for each bag, based on their experience during the task. This third estimate captured participants' understanding of the new outcome contingencies introduced in the second phase of the task. These self-generated probability judgments served as an index of belief updating. An insufficient change in these estimates across the two time points indicated bias persistence, reflecting limited integration of new feedback into belief systems.

Choice behavior was monitored throughout the Free Sampling Phase, during which participants made 84 voluntary selections between the two options. Behavioral bias persistence was defined as a significant and persistent tendency to select the initially favored option. Continued reliance on an early-formed preference, despite potential contradictory feedback, was interpreted as a marker of decision-making rigidity. This operationalization aligns with prior studies showing that reduced flexibility in choice behavior is a hallmark of trauma-exposed individuals facing emotionally salient or ambiguous feedback (Paulus & Yu, 2012).

Physiological Arousal - Skin Conductance Response

Electrodermal activity (EDA) was recorded continuously throughout the task as an index of physiological arousal. EDA reflects changes in skin conductance linked to

sympathetic nervous system activity and emotional reactivity (Critchley, 2002). From this continuous signal, skin conductance responses (SCRs) were isolated during the anticipatory period between participants' choices and the presentation of the outcome, in order to assess phasic arousal related to decision-making. EDA was recorded continuously during both experimental phases using a Biopac MP160 system with AcqKnowledge software. Electrodes were attached to the left hand's index and middle fingers in accordance with standard electrodermal recording procedures (Boucsein et al., 2012). The primary psychophysiological variable of interest was the anticipatory skin conductance response (aSCR), defined as the average amplitude of phasic electrodermal activity during the 3-second interval between a participant's choice and the presentation of feedback. This anticipatory window was selected because it is sensitive to threat anticipation and internalized emotional responses, especially among trauma-exposed populations (Orr & Roth, 2000). Higher aSCR in this period suggests heightened arousal and emotional investment in the potential consequences of one's decisions. To assess physiological bias persistence, within-participant comparisons were conducted between aSCR values following selections of the participant's more preferred versus less preferred option. A significantly greater aSCR when selecting the less preferred bag indicated emotional reactivity, consistent with threat anticipation mechanisms often observed in individuals with PTSD and CPTSD (Etkin & Wager, 2007; Keane, Marshall, & Taft, 2006). Raw SCR data were pre-processed using model-based decomposition techniques to extract clean phasic components on a per-trial basis (Benedek & Kaernbach, 2010), offering enhanced precision over traditional peak-to-peak scoring. Together, these measures enabled the triangulation of cognitive, emotional, and physiological components of decision-making under uncertainty, yielding a multi-dimensional perspective on how trauma-related symptoms may drive bias persistence in emotionally charged contexts.

Data Analysis

The final sample for behavioral and self-report analyses consisted of $N = 87$ participants. Initially, 103 individuals took part in the experiment. However, in line with pre-registered exclusion criteria, 16 participants were removed from the primary analyses to ensure the quality and interpretability of the data. Specifically, participants were excluded if they (a) failed to form an initial bias during the Bias Induction Phase, (b) terminated the task prematurely, or (c) reported prior participation in a highly similar study. These exclusions

were necessary to isolate participants whose behavior could be meaningfully interpreted in relation to belief updating and bias persistence.

In addition to these exclusions for the primary behavioral analyses, a further 4 participants were excluded from analyses involving physiological data, specifically skin conductance responses (SCR), due to incomplete or unusable SCR recordings. As a result, the final sample used for SCR analyses comprised 83 participants.

To assess whether trauma-related symptomatology predicted bias persistence at the overall (participant) level, a multiple linear regression was conducted. The dependent variable was the proportion of trials in the Free Sampling Phase during which participants selected their initially preferred option (*select_best2_rate*), which served as a behavioral index of decision rigidity. Predictor variables included standardized PTSD and DSO scores, obtained from the ITQ, along with baseline contingency estimates (*dP_pre*), which reflected participants' initial beliefs about choice-outcome contingencies before exposure to aversive stimuli. A higher proportion of biased choices would suggest less belief updating and greater reliance on early-formed preferences, consistent with bias persistence.

To explore moment-to-moment decision-making dynamics, a generalized linear mixed-effects model (GLMM) with a binomial link function was fitted to the trial-level data. The binary outcome variable (*select_best2*) captured whether the participant chose their initially favored option on each trial during the Free Sampling Phase. Fixed effects included standardized PTSD and DSO scores, Trial number (to capture time-based changes in decision behavior), experimental Condition (Highly Aversive vs. Less Aversive), and the Trial \times Condition interaction. A random intercept for participant ID (Ppn) was included to account for repeated observations within individuals and inter-individual variability in choice patterns.

To examine whether the emotional intensity of the task moderated the relationship between trauma symptoms and biased behavior, a follow-up GLMM was estimated. This model included interaction terms between PTSD and Condition as well as DSO and Condition. Continuous predictors were z-standardized, and Condition was effect-coded to allow interpretation of both main effects and moderation. This allowed for testing whether trauma symptoms were differentially associated with bias persistence depending on whether participants were in the high-stress or low-stress version of the task.

To examine whether physiological arousal was associated with trauma symptoms or experimental condition, skin conductance responses (SCRs) were analyzed during the anticipatory period between participants' choices and outcome presentations. SCR data were preprocessed using the PsPM toolbox, implemented in MATLAB. Specifically, a dynamic causal model (DCM) was estimated for each participant to account for variability in the onset latency, amplitude, and shape of anticipatory responses. This model-based approach offers improved temporal precision compared to traditional peak scoring, and allows for more accurate isolation of phasic arousal signals time-locked to decision events (Bach & Friston, 2013). Following preprocessing and model inversion, mean anticipatory SCR amplitudes were extracted for each participant across all valid trials. These values were then log-transformed to correct for skewness and ensure a more normal distribution suitable for parametric analysis.

Together, these models enabled a comprehensive analysis of bias persistence by examining both individual-level tendencies and trial-level decision patterns, while also considering the interaction between internal symptomatology and external emotional context.

Results

Descriptive Statistics

The final sample for the behavioral and survey data consisted of 87 participants who met all inclusion criteria and completed the full experimental procedure. Descriptive statistics for all key variables are presented in Table 1. Scores on the PTSD subscale of the International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ) ranged from 6 to 25, with a mean of 13.59 (SD = 4.94), while scores on the DSO subscale ranged from 6 to 27 (M = 13.54, SD = 5.15). The combined ITQ total scores, representing overall trauma symptomatology, ranged from 12 to 47 (M = 27.13, SD = 8.61), with values normally distributed across participants. Approximately 34% of participants scored above 30 on the ITQ total scale, indicating that a meaningful subset of the sample reported elevated trauma-related symptomatology. While the ITQ does not provide a formal cutoff for high severity, scores in this range have been associated with increased clinical relevance in previous research (Cloitre et al., 2018).

Participants' behavioral bias, as measured by the proportion of trials in which they selected the initially preferred option during the Free Sampling Phase (`select_best2_rate`),

ranged from 0.00 to 1.00, with an average of 0.57 ($SD = 0.50$). Only a small number of participants ($n = 2$) consistently avoided the initially preferred option ($select_best2_rate = 0$), and another small group ($n = 2$) consistently selected it throughout the Free Sampling Phase ($select_best2_rate = 1$). This suggests that most participants alternated between exploitative choices (favoring their initial preference) and explorative choices (sampling the alternative option), rather than exclusively committing to one strategy across the task. This indicates that, on average, participants chose the previously favored option in over half of the trials, even when new outcome evidence was available. This pattern suggests the presence of some degree of bias persistence across the sample.

Table 1
Descriptive Statistics for Key Variables

Variable	M	SD	Min	Max
PTSD (ITQ)	13.59	4.50	6.00	25.0
DSO (ITQ)	13.54	4.49	6.00	27.0
ITQ Total	27.13	8.09	12.00	47.0
Bias Persistence	0.57	0.16	0.00	1.0
Initial Belief (dP_pre)	0.14	0.26	-0.54	0.8
Post Belief (dP)	0.01	0.19	-0.60	0.6
Belief Change	0.21	0.26	-0.50	1.0

Baseline contingency estimates (dP_pre), representing participants' initial expectations before encountering the aversive feedback, ranged from -0.54 to 0.80 ($M = 0.14$, $SD = 0.25$), indicating moderate variation in early belief formation. Post-feedback contingency estimates (dP) were more normally distributed, ranging from -0.60 to 0.60 ($M = 0.01$, $SD = 0.17$), suggesting that belief updating was variable across individuals. The belief change score (dP_pre2 - dP2), computed to reflect the degree to which participants updated their initial beliefs in response to outcome feedback, was also positively skewed ($M = 0.15$, $SD = 0.26$), indicating some overall adjustment but with individual differences in flexibility.

The correlation between PTSD and DSO scores was moderate and statistically significant, $r = .62$, $p < .001$, consistent with previous research suggesting partial overlap

between core PTSD symptoms and broader disturbances in affect regulation and self-concept. All variables demonstrated acceptable levels of variability and were suitable for parametric modeling.

Hypothesis 1 – Trauma Symptoms Predict Behavioral Bias Persistence

The regression model as a whole was not statistically significant, $F(3, 83) = 1.88, p = .14, R^2 = .06$, indicating that only a modest proportion of variance in choice behavior was accounted for by the included predictors. However, an examination of the individual predictors revealed meaningful patterns consistent with theoretical expectations. PTSD emerged as a significant positive predictor of biased decision-making behavior ($\beta = .30, SE = 0.14, p = .030$), suggesting that individuals with higher levels of PTSD symptoms were more likely to persist in their initial choice pattern, even in the face of disconfirming evidence.

By contrast, DSO symptoms showed a marginally significant negative association with bias persistence ($\beta = -.27, SE = 0.14, p = .050$), indicating a potential protective effect against rigid decision-making. That is, individuals reporting higher levels of DSO symptoms, characterized by affective dysregulation, negative self-concept, and interpersonal difficulties, were somewhat less likely to persist in the use of an outdated decision strategy. Although this effect was only marginal, it suggests that the relationship between trauma symptoms and behavioral rigidity may differ across distinct dimensions of symptomatology. As shown in Figure 1, higher PTSD scores were associated with increased bias persistence. The association between DSO symptoms and bias persistence is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 1

Scatterplot with fitted regression line showing the relationship between PTSD scores and bias persistence (proportion of biased choices). Higher PTSD scores were associated with increased bias persistence.

Figure 2

Scatterplot with fitted regression line showing the relationship between DSO scores and bias persistence. Higher DSO scores were marginally associated with lower bias persistence.

Baseline contingency estimates (dP_{pre}), which reflect participants' initial beliefs about the magnitude of outcome contingencies before exposure to aversive stimuli, were not significantly associated with later behavior ($\beta = .02$, $SE = 0.07$, $p = .86$). This implies that early beliefs did not substantially influence the extent to which participants updated or maintained their choices over time, reinforcing the notion that trauma symptoms exert a more prominent effect on behavioral persistence than initial belief strength.

Table 2

Multiple Linear Regression Predicting Bias Persistence from PTSD, DSO, and Baseline Beliefs

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p
Intercept	0.559	0.063		8.89	< .001
PTSD	0.011	0.14	0.30	2.22	.030
DSO	-0.010	0.005	-0.27	-1.99	.050
ΔP	0.012	0.066	0.02	0.18	.860

Note. $R^2 = .06$, Adjusted $R^2 = .03$, $F(3, 83) = 1.88$, $p = .14$

In addition to the effects of PTSD and DSO, the intercept of the model was also statistically significant ($p < .001$), indicating that participants, on average, selected the initially preferred option at a rate significantly above chance (0.50). This suggests an overall tendency to persist in early preferences, regardless of trauma symptom severity or initial belief strength.

Taken together, these findings provide partial support for Hypothesis 1. Specifically, PTSD symptoms appear to increase vulnerability to bias persistence, consistent with models suggesting that trauma impairs cognitive flexibility and promotes reliance on habitual, emotionally "safer" behaviors. In contrast, DSO may be associated with slightly greater openness to behavioral change, although this effect did not reach conventional levels of significance. These divergent patterns underscore the importance of differentiating between PTSD and CPTSD symptom dimensions when evaluating cognitive outcomes in trauma-exposed individuals.

Hypothesis 2: Trial-Level Effects of Trauma Symptoms on Biased Choice

The model revealed a significant main effect of PTSD ($\beta = 0.054$, $SE = 0.025$, $z = 2.11$, $p = .035$), indicating that individuals with higher PTSD symptom severity were more likely to

make biased choices on a trial-by-trial basis. In contrast, DSO symptoms showed a marginally significant negative association with biased choice behavior ($\beta = -0.049$, $SE = 0.025$, $z = -1.94$, $p = .052$), suggesting that individuals with higher DSO scores were somewhat less likely to engage in biased decision-making.

Neither Trial number ($\beta = -0.001$, $p = .72$) nor its interaction with Condition ($\beta = 0.002$, $p = .64$) were significant, indicating no overall time trend in bias and no condition-specific changes across trials. The main effect of Condition was also non-significant ($\beta = -0.079$, $p = .66$), suggesting that the emotional context did not independently influence the likelihood of biased choices. Figure 3 depicts the predicted trial-level probability of biased choices as a function of DSO symptom severity.

Table 3

Fixed Effects from the Generalized Linear Mixed-Effects Model (GLMM) at the Trial Level

Predictor	B	SE	z	p
Intercept	0.396	0.423	0.94	.35
PTSD	0.054	0.025	2.11	.035
DSO	-0.049	0.025	-1.94	.052
Condition	-0.079	0.179	-0.44	.66

Note. Results from a generalized linear mixed-effects model (GLMM) with a binomial link function predicting biased choice behavior (select_best2) on the trial level. PTSD and DSO scores were entered as continuous predictors. Condition was dummy coded (1 = Low Aversiveness, 2 = High Aversiveness). A random intercept was included for participant ID.

Figure 3

Predicted probability of biased choice as a function of DSO symptom severity. Higher DSO scores were associated with a reduced likelihood of biased responding on a trial-by-trial basis. Shaded area represents 95% confidence intervals.

These results align with those from Hypothesis 1, providing further support that PTSD symptoms are associated with greater rigidity in decision-making under uncertainty. In contrast, DSO symptoms may be linked to a slight increase in behavioral flexibility, although this effect was only marginal. Trial-level modelling reinforces this interpretation by showing that these effects persist across repeated decisions within individuals.

Overall, Hypothesis 2 was partially supported: PTSD symptoms significantly predicted increased trial-level bias persistence, while DSO showed a trend toward reduced biased responding. The absence of a condition effect suggests that individual trauma-related traits play a stronger role than transient emotional context in shaping decision-making behavior.

Hypothesis 3: Moderating Role of Condition (Aversiveness) on Trauma Effects

Consistent with previous models, PTSD remained a significant positive predictor of biased choice behavior at the trial level ($\beta = 0.25$, $SE = 0.11$, $z = 2.30$, $p = .021$). This indicates that even when accounting for potential moderation by Condition, higher levels of PTSD symptomatology continued to predict greater persistence in selecting the initially preferred option, despite the presence of contradictory evidence. Similarly, DSO scores were again significantly negatively associated with biased responding ($\beta = -0.28$, $SE = 0.11$, $z = -2.50$, $p = .012$), suggesting a consistent pattern in which higher levels of CPTSD symptoms were related to decreased behavioral rigidity and greater openness to decision adjustment. The full results of this moderation model are presented in Table 4. The distribution of bias persistence across aversiveness conditions is illustrated in Figure 4.

Table 4*Moderation of Trauma Effects on Biased Choice by Aversiveness Condition*

Predictor	Estimate (β)	SE	z	p
PTSD	0.25	0.11	2.3	0.021
DSO	-0.28	0.11	-2.5	0.012
Condition (effect-coded)	0.04	0.18	0.22	0.825
PTSD \times Condition	0.07	0.08	0.92	0.359
DSO \times Condition	-0.02	0.09	-0.22	0.83

Note. Standardized predictors were used for PTSD and DSO (z-scored). Condition was effect-coded (Low = -0.5, High = 0.5).

Bias persistence was modeled at the trial level using a generalized linear mixed-effects model with a binomial link. B = unstandardized estimate; SE = standard error.

Figure 4

Bias Persistence by Aversiveness Condition Violin plots show the distribution of the proportion of biased choices (selecting the initially preferred option) across participants in the Low and High Aversiveness conditions. While the average levels of bias were similar between conditions, individual variability was observed in both groups.

In contrast, the interaction terms testing whether the strength of these associations varied by emotional intensity of decision-making context were not statistically significant. Specifically, the PTSD \times Condition interaction did not reach significance ($p = .359$), nor did the DSO \times Condition interaction ($p = .830$). These results indicate that the effects of trauma symptoms on biased decision-making were stable across both low and high aversiveness conditions. In other words, there was no evidence that the emotional intensity of the task context amplified or attenuated the influence of PTSD or DSO symptoms on decision-making behavior.

A linear model including standardized PTSD and DSO scores revealed no significant association between trauma symptoms and mean SCR amplitude. Specifically, PTSD was not a significant predictor ($\beta = 0.02, p = .912$), nor was DSO ($\beta = -0.006, p = .965$). Prior to analysis, SCRs were preprocessed using PsPM (Bach & Friston, 2013). A dynamic causal model (DCM) was applied to estimate anticipatory phasic responses while flexibly accounting for onset latency during the interval between participants' choices and outcome presentations. Mean SCR amplitudes were computed per participant across valid trials and log-transformed to correct for non-normal distribution. These findings suggest that individual differences in trauma-related symptoms were not associated with overall physiological reactivity during decision anticipation.

To examine whether emotional context moderated the relationship between trauma symptoms and arousal, a follow-up model included interaction terms between PTSD, DSO, and Condition. This model also did not yield significant effects for PTSD \times Condition ($p = .877$), though a marginal interaction emerged for DSO \times Condition ($p = .061$), suggesting a potential trend toward differential arousal patterns based on symptom severity and task condition. However, this trend should be interpreted cautiously due to the non-significance of the overall model ($F(5, 75) = 1.13, p = .35$). Skin conductance responses across aversiveness conditions and DSO levels are shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5

SCR by Condition across DSO Levels

Taken together, these results suggest that trauma-related cognitive rigidity in decision-making was not directly linked to general physiological arousal, and that the influence of PTSD and DSO on biased behavior appears to operate through cognitive-affective mechanisms rather than heightened autonomic activation.

These findings suggest that individual differences in trauma symptomatology exert a more robust influence on bias persistence than do situational emotional cues. The lack of significant moderation effects implies that the cognitive and behavioral tendencies associated with PTSD and DSO operate relatively independently of transient environmental factors. This supports the notion that trauma-related rigidity or flexibility in decision-making may reflect more stable internal processes, such as cognitive avoidance or emotional dysregulation, rather than being strongly modulated by current affective context.

Exploratory Analysis

To examine whether trauma symptoms influenced how biased decision-making evolved over time, an exploratory generalized linear mixed-effects model was fitted, including PTSD and DSO (standardized), Trial number, Condition, and their interactions with Trial as fixed effects, along with a random intercept for participant ID ($N = 87$; $n = 7,308$ trials).

PTSD was positively associated with biased choice behavior ($\beta = 0.26$, $p = .041$), while DSO was negatively associated ($\beta = -0.33$, $p = .008$). The interaction between DSO and Trial

was significant ($\beta = 0.003, p = .039$), suggesting that the protective effect of DSO on bias weakened as the task progressed. In contrast, the PTSD \times Trial interaction was not significant ($\beta = -0.0005, p = .73$), indicating that PTSD-related bias persisted consistently over time.

Although the interaction between Trial and Condition was tested in a preliminary model, it was excluded from the final specification due to its non-significance and to favor model parsimony. This suggests no evidence for condition-specific changes in bias over time.

Together, these findings indicate that while PTSD symptoms were linked to a sustained tendency for biased responding, DSO symptoms may contribute to improved behavioral adaptation over time.

Figure 6

Predicted proportion of biased choices across trials by PTSD severity (z-standardized).

To further examine whether physiological arousal was related to decision-making rigidity, an exploratory linear model tested whether log-transformed skin conductance responses (SCR_log) predicted bias persistence at the participant level. The analysis revealed no significant association between anticipatory physiological reactivity and biased choice behavior ($\beta = -0.05, p = .64$). This lack of relationship supports the interpretation that trauma-related differences in bias persistence are more likely driven by cognitive-affective mechanisms than by heightened autonomic arousal.

Discussion

This study aimed to investigate how trauma-related symptoms affect bias persistence in emotionally aversive decision-making. The primary focus was whether symptoms of PTSD and CPTSD (particularly disturbances in self-organization, or DSO) are associated with greater rigidity in behavior and belief updating. Overall, results showed that higher PTSD symptoms predicted more biased behavior and impaired belief updating, consistent with cognitive rigidity. In contrast, DSO symptoms showed marginal or opposite associations, indicating potentially greater flexibility. While emotional intensity did not moderate these effects, and no effects were found for physiological arousal, findings provide insights into differential trauma symptom pathways in decision-making.

PTSD and Cognitive Rigidity

As expected, higher PTSD symptoms were significantly associated with increased bias persistence. This supports existing findings linking PTSD with behavioral inflexibility and difficulties in updating beliefs under uncertainty. The predictive value of PTSD symptoms across both outcome measures (select_best2_rate and contingency estimates) strengthens the view that trauma-related rigidity manifests in both decision patterns and learning processes. Participants with higher PTSD symptoms were more likely to stick with previously rewarded options, even when contingencies shifted, and were less able to update beliefs in response to feedback. This may reflect maladaptive safety-seeking behaviors or overgeneralized threat responses that impair flexible thinking.

These findings align with studies showing that PTSD is linked to persistent fear responses and impaired extinction learning. In real-world settings, this could mean that trauma-affected individuals struggle to adapt to new information, maintaining rigid beliefs about danger or self-worth even when those beliefs are no longer supported. Our data reinforce the notion that PTSD may involve disruptions in prediction error processing, crucial for adaptive behavior.

CPTSD and Relative Flexibility

In contrast to PTSD, CPTSD's DSO symptoms showed either non-significant or marginally opposite effects, particularly on choice behavior. Participants with higher DSO scores showed slightly less bias persistence, suggesting greater behavioral flexibility. While belief updating was not significantly affected, the directionality supports the idea that DSO may relate to different cognitive dynamics than PTSD.

This finding may reflect that while PTSD is linked to hypervigilance and fear-based rigidity, DSO may involve greater internal focus (e.g., self-perception, emotion dysregulation), possibly affecting decision-making differently. Research suggests that individuals with CPTSD may engage in avoidance or numbing rather than active threat monitoring, which could lessen the grip of conditioned responses in decision-making contexts. However, due to small effect sizes and marginal significance, these interpretations should be taken cautiously and require replication.

Lack of Moderation by Emotional Intensity

Contrary to expectations, the manipulation of emotional intensity did not moderate the effects of trauma symptoms. Participants were equally affected by high- and low-intensity conditions, regardless of trauma profile. While prior literature suggests that emotional arousal amplifies trauma-related cognitive deficits, our findings did not support this interaction.

There are a few possible explanations. First, emotional reactivity might already be elevated in trauma-exposed individuals, making the additional manipulation less impactful. Second, individual differences in sensitivity may override the condition-based differences. Finally, the manipulation might not have been strong or consistent enough to interact with symptomatology at a behavioral level. Future studies could use stronger or more personally relevant aversive stimuli to test this more effectively.

SCR Results and Physiological Reactivity

No significant relationships were found between trauma symptoms and physiological reactivity (SCR) to worst versus preferred cues or US anticipation. This suggests that, at least in this task, anticipatory arousal was not reliably linked to trauma profiles.

This contrasts with some research showing hyperarousal in PTSD. However, SCR responses can vary widely, and task-specific factors may influence measurement. It's possible that decision-making and physiological arousal were more weakly coupled in this sample or that our SCR indices were not sensitive to trauma-related differences. Future research might consider more dynamic or personally relevant arousal measures.

Implications

The findings provide novel insights into the distinct cognitive profiles associated with PTSD and CPTSD symptoms. The strong association between PTSD and bias persistence

highlights the role of trauma in disrupting adaptive learning and flexibility, processes crucial for navigating uncertainty. Understanding this rigidity has implications for clinical interventions, such as targeting cognitive flexibility or updating trauma-related beliefs in therapy.

Conversely, the relative flexibility associated with DSO symptoms could suggest a different therapeutic focus. Rather than addressing threat bias, treatments for CPTSD might more effectively target affect regulation and identity processes without necessarily focusing on rigid decision-making.

Limitations

Several limitations should be noted. First, this was a non-clinical sample with subthreshold PTSD/CPTSD symptom levels, limiting generalizability. Second, self-report measures of trauma symptoms may not capture clinical nuance or diagnostic categories. Third, the aversive manipulation may not have been intense or variable enough to interact meaningfully with trauma symptoms. Fourth, while the sample size ($N = 87$) is adequate for exploratory modeling, statistical power may have been limited for detecting interaction effects or small associations.

Finally, physiological measures like SCR were noisy and may have required greater trial counts or baseline correction for more reliable detection of group differences.

Conclusion

This study adds to growing evidence that trauma symptoms, particularly PTSD, are linked to inflexible decision-making and disrupted belief updating. The marginally opposite patterns for CPTSD's DSO symptoms suggest distinct mechanisms underlying trauma-related cognitive processing. Although emotional intensity and physiological arousal did not moderate these relationships, the findings highlight symptom-specific effects that could inform targeted interventions. Future research should replicate these findings in clinical samples and use more refined physiological and emotional assessments to further uncover the mechanisms driving trauma-related cognitive bias.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Information Letter

Universiteit Utrecht

Information Letter – Fear learning and decision-making under uncertainty – Experiment 3

Dear participant,

You are reading this information letter because you gave us your contact information regarding participation in our study. With this letter, we would like to invite you to participate in the study entitled “**Fear learning and decision-making under uncertainty**”. Participation is voluntary. Your permission is required in order to participate. Before the experiment starts, it is important that you are informed about the procedures. Therefore, we would like you to read this information letter carefully. Please do not hesitate to ask the test leader for clarification about this text or the study’s procedure. If anything is unclear, the researcher will answer your questions. If you would like further clarification in Dutch, please ask the researcher for more information.

The purpose of this research

The purpose of this research is to investigate threat response and decision-making behavior when presented with threat. More specifically, we will investigate skin conductance and self-reported expectations. This study is performed by a PhD student and three master’s students as part of their research projects.

Eligibility

To take part in this research, you need to:

- Have normal or corrected to normal vision (meaning: you wear prescription glasses or lenses);
- Not suffer from epilepsy or a related condition;
- Have no (history of) cardiac, or neurological disorders;

Please contact us if you have any questions about these criteria.

The procedure of the research

In this research, you will be asked to perform a computer task. During the experiment, sudden loud noises will be delivered through the headphones. The volume and duration of these noises is determined so that no risk of hearing damage is involved. Before the experiment starts, you will hear an example of the noise used, after which you will be asked whether you are OK continuing with the rest of the experiment. We will set you up with electrodes on your wrist and your hands to continuously measure your skin conductance responses during the experiment. Afterwards, you can proceed with the computer task in which you will make decisions and then observe the outcomes. In the main part of the experiment, this outcome is the loud noise, which will occur with an unknown probability for each decision. During this task, we will provide short breaks so that you can rest and recover if necessary. The computer task will be further explained in detail during the study. Your participation will take about 60 minutes of your time.

Voluntary participation

There are no consequences if you now decide not to participate in this study. During the experiment, you are free to stop participating at any moment without giving a reason for doing so. You will still be compensated for your time in the study if you decide to stop participating after the study has begun.

Your privacy is guaranteed

Your data will be processed in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation. Your personal information (about who you are) that we collect for consent and compensation purposes will remain confidential and will be stored separately from the research data. Your research data will be labeled with a code that cannot be traced back to you, and analyzed by the researchers that collected the information, other researchers within the research group and/or the principal investigators. Research data published in scientific journals will be anonymous and cannot be traced back to you as an individual. Completely anonymized data can be shared with other researchers or made publicly accessible. For more information and questions about privacy see <https://www.uu.nl/en/organisation/data-protection-officer>.

Potential advantages and disadvantages for participating

There are no advantages for the participant by participating in this study. However, your participation may contribute to a better understanding of the human brain and behavior.

Apart from potential discomfort from the noises, uncertainty and electrode application, there are no foreseen disadvantages or risks for participating in this study. While the noises are played at a high volume, their duration is limited. Over the entire experiment, you will not be exposed to more than 1.5 minutes of a 100 dB noise, which is well below the threshold for potential hearing damage (you can find more information about this threshold on oorcheck.nl). In addition, we will provide regular moments of rest inbetween trials.

Compensation

As compensation for your participation, you will receive 8 euros or 1 PPU (*proefpersoonuren*) per hour.

How to get more information and how to act in case of complaints

For questions about privacy you can contact privacy@uu.nl. If you have complaints regarding this study, please discuss this with the researcher first. Lead researcher is Emily Vanlooy, Faculty of Social Sciences, Utrecht University (E-mail: e.a.vanlooy@uu.nl). If you want to get in touch with an independent researcher within the research group, you can contact Livia Regus (E-mail: l.regus@uu.nl). If your complaint is not resolved satisfactorily, it is possible to report this to the complaints officer of the Faculty of Social Sciences, Utrecht University (E-mail: klachtenfunctionaris-fetsocwet@uu.nl).

For further information contact the executive researcher

Emily Vanlooy, PhD candidate UU

Contact information: e.a.vanlooy@uu.nl

Appendix B: Consent Form**Universiteit Utrecht****Consent form fear learning and decision-making under uncertainty – Experiment 3**

- I have read the participant information letter. I was able to ask additional questions. My questions have been answered and I had enough time to decide.
- I know that participating is entirely voluntary. I know I can decide at any time not to participate without having to give a reason.
- I know that my anonymized data can be viewed by researchers.
- I give permission to use my data, for the purposes stated in the information letter.
- I want to participate in this study.

Subject name:

Signature:

Date :

- I hereby declare that I have fully informed this subject about the aforementioned research.

Name of researcher (or his/her representative):

Signature:

Date:

Appendix C : International Trauma Questionnaire (ITQ)

International Trauma Questionnaire

Instructions: Please identify the experience that troubles you most and answer the questions in relation to this experience.

Brief description of the experience _____

When did the experience occur? (circle one)

- a. less than 6 months ago
- b. 6 to 12 months ago
- c. 1 to 5 years ago
- d. 5 to 10 years ago
- e. 10 to 20 years ago
- f. more than 20 years ago

Below are a number of problems that people sometimes report in response to traumatic or stressful life events. Please read each item carefully, then circle one of the numbers to the right to indicate how much you have been bothered by that problem in the past month.

	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>A little bit</i>	<i>Moderately</i>	<i>Quite a bit</i>	<i>Extremely</i>
P1. Having upsetting dreams that replay part of the experience or are clearly related to the experience?	0	1	2	3	4
P2. Having powerful images or memories that sometimes come into your mind in which you feel the experience is happening again in the here and now?	0	1	2	3	4
P3. Avoiding internal reminders of the experience (for example, thoughts, feelings, or physical sensations)?	0	1	2	3	4
P4. Avoiding external reminders of the experience (for example, people, places, conversations, objects, activities, or situations)?	0	1	2	3	4
P5. Being "super-alert", watchful, or on guard?	0	1	2	3	4
P6. Feeling jumpy or easily startled?	0	1	2	3	4

In the past month have the above problems:

P7. Affected your relationships or social life?	0	1	2	3	4
P8. Affected your work or ability to work?	0	1	2	3	4
P9. Affected any other important part of your life such as parenting, or school or college work, or other important activities?	0	1	2	3	4

Below are problems that people who have had stressful or traumatic events sometimes experience. The questions refer to ways you typically feel, ways you typically think about yourself and ways you typically relate to others. Answer the following thinking about how true each statement is of you.

<i>How true is this of you?</i>	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>A little bit</i>	<i>Moderately</i>	<i>Quite a bit</i>	<i>Extremely</i>
C1. When I am upset, it takes me a long time to calm down.	0	1	2	3	4
C2. I feel numb or emotionally shut down.	0	1	2	3	4
C3. I feel like a failure.	0	1	2	3	4
C4. I feel worthless.	0	1	2	3	4
C5. I feel distant or cut off from people.	0	1	2	3	4
C6. I find it hard to stay emotionally close to people.	0	1	2	3	4
<i>In the past month, have the above problems in emotions, in beliefs about yourself and in relationships:</i>					
C7. Created concern or distress about your relationships or social life?	0	1	2	3	4
C8. Affected your work or ability to work?	0	1	2	3	4
C9. Affected any other important parts of your life such as parenting, or school or college work, or other important activities?	0	1	2	3	4